

Potentiometric Studies in Oxidation-Reduction Reactions. Part I. Oxidation with Potassium Iodate.

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Potassium iodate was first used by Andrews (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 25, 756) for the titration of a number of reducing substances such as free iodine, iodides, arsenites and antimonites in presence of a large excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The method depends upon the formation of iodine monochloride and the disappearance of the iodine colour imparted to an immiscible solvent such as chloroform or carbon tetrachloride.

Lang (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 122, 332) has carried out fundamental investigations concerning direct titrations with potassium iodate in the presence of hydrogen cyanide. The end-point is again the disappearance of the iodine colour due to the formation of cyanide. The similarity of the two methods may be illustrated by the stoichiometric equations for the estimation of iodides.

In all the reactions the iodate, in effecting oxidation, is reduced to iodide, which reacts with more iodate producing iodine, and this in turn reacts with more iodate to complete the reaction (Mitchel and Ward. "Modern Methods in Quantitative Chemical Analysis." 1932, p. 2).

Schoonover and Furman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 3123) studied the oxidation of arsenious oxide with potassium iodate in hydrochloric and sulphuric acid solutions by a potentiometric method. They found that the concentration of the acid was an important factor in oxidation in hydrochloric acid. They proved that iodide, iodine or iodine monochloride were formed as the final reduction products of the iodate in the oxidation of arsenic depending upon the hydrogen-

ion concentration. In a solution 4 to 6 normal in hydrochloric acid, iodine monochloride was formed as the final product.

The great stability of the potassium iodate solution and its non-interference with many kinds of organic matter make these methods applicable to cases in which the potassium permanganate method could not be used satisfactorily.

Jamieson ("Volumetric Iodate Methods", 1926) has made a thorough investigation into the applicability of Andrew's method. He has shown that it is advantageous in a few cases, particularly where very small quantities of a substance are to be determined, to add a small quantity of iodine monochloride dissolved in hydrochloric acid and to titrate the liberated iodine against potassium iodate solution.

In the present investigation thalious, stannous, mercurous, antimonious, and arsenious salts have been determined potentiometrically by titrating against standard potassium iodate in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The oxidation-reduction electrode, which consisted of a bright platinum foil immersed in the solution to be titrated, was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode through an agar-agar-KCl bridge. The cell was placed in a water-bath, the temperature of which was maintained at 10°. The E. M. F. of the cell was read on a potentiometer scale (Potentiometer, Cambridge Instrument Co. Ltd., England).

A standard solution of potassium iodate was prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity of the pure dry analytical reagent in the water. The solution required no further standardisation and was permanent. According to Jamieson (*loc. cit.*) a solution of potassium iodate was kept for 10 years without a change of strength.

A known weight of each salt was weighed into a titration vessel and the required amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid added to keep its concentration above 4*N*. Standard potassium iodate was added from a burette, the mixture stirred by a mechanical stirrer and the progress of the oxidation followed with the potentiometer.

A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each salt. One titration for every salt, as typical of that set, is recorded in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Titration of thalious chloride (0.1193 g.) mixed with 20 c.c. of water and 25 c.c. of conc. HCl, against KIO_3 ($M/20$).

KIO_3 .	E. M. F. (volts).	$\Delta E/\Delta C$ (m. volt/c.c.).
3.50 c.c.	0.520	
		60
4.00	0.550	
		90
4.40	0.586	
		85
4.60	0.603	
		100
4.80	0.623	
		193
4.95	0.652	
		<u>4660</u>
5.00	0.885	
		500
5.05	0.910	
		300
5.10	0.925	
		125
5.30	0.950	
		40
5.80	0.970	
		5
6.80	0.975	

TABLE II.

Titration of stannous chloride (0.1127 g.) mixed with 20 c.c. of water and 25 c.c. of conc. HCl, against KIO_3 ($M/20$).

KIO_3 .	E. M. F. (volts).	$\Delta E/\Delta C$ (m. volt/c.c.).
4.00 c.c.	0.528	
		105
4.20	0.549	
		80
4.40	0.565	
		100
4.60	0.585	
		105
4.80	0.606	
		120
4.90	0.618	
		380
4.95	0.637	
		<u>4060</u>
5.00	0.840	
		300
5.10	0.870	
		110
5.30	0.892	
		36
5.80	0.910	
		8
6.80	0.918	

TABLE III.

Titration of mercurous chloride (0.2354 g.) mixed with 20 c.c. of water and 25 c.c. of conc. HCl, against KIO_3 ($M/20$)

KIO_3	E M F (volt).	$\Delta E/\Delta C$ (m volt/c.c.).
3.00 c.c.	0.504	
		37
4.00	0.541	54
4.50	0.568	85
4.70	0.585	90
4.80	0.594	507
4.95	0.670	<u>4000</u>
5.00	0.870	480
5.05	0.894	320
5.10	0.910	200
5.20	0.930	33
5.50	0.940	33
5.80	0.950	6
6.80	0.956	

TABLE IV.

Titration of potassium antimonyl tartrate (0.3240 g.) mixed with 20 c.c. of water and 25 c.c. of conc. HCl, against KIO_3 ($M/20$).

KIO_3 .	E. M F (volt)	$\Delta E/\Delta C$ (m volt/c.c.)
9.00 c.c.	0.630	30
9.20	0.636	30
9.40	0.642	25
9.60	0.647	45
9.80	0.656	70
9.90	0.663	120
9.95	0.669	<u>3520</u>
10.00	0.845	100
10.05	0.850	100
10.15	0.860	80
10.40	0.880	38
10.80	0.895	13
11.80	0.908	

TABLE V.

Titration of arsenious oxide (0.0989 g) mixed with 20 c.c. of water and 25 c.c. of conc. HCl, against KIO_3 ($M/20$).

KIO_3 .	E M F (volt).	$\Delta E/\Delta C$ (m volt/c.c.)	KIO_3 .	E M F (volt).	$\Delta E/\Delta C$ (m. volt/c.c.)
8.00 c.c.	0.482		9.95	0.628	
		54			<u>4240</u>
9.00	0.536	63	10.00	0.840	500
9.40	0.561	75	10.05	0.865	230
9.60	0.576	70	10.15	0.888	45
9.80	0.590	140	10.35	0.897	36
9.90	0.604	<u>480</u>	10.85	0.915	14
			11.90	0.930	

The curves for the above titration are given in Fig. 1.

D I S C U S S I O N.

In these titrations, with the addition of standard potassium iodate the E. M. F. rose steadily till the equivalence point. At the equivalence-point, there was a sharp jump in potential in each case. For the addition of 0.05 c.c. of the titrant, the inflection potential was of the order of 233, 203, 200, 176 and 212 millivolts for thalious chloride, stannous chloride, mercurous chloride, potassium antimonyl tartrate and arsenious oxide respectively. After the equivalence-point, there was again a rise in the potential which became steady on further addition of the reagent.

FIG 1.
Potassium iodate titration.

Curves 1—5 refer respectively to thalious chloride, stannous chloride, sodium arsenite, mercurous chloride and pot. antim. tartrate.

From the volume of the potassium iodate solution required in each titration corresponding to the equivalence-point, the amount of the salt was calculated. The values obtained are compared with the amounts of the salt taken in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Thalious chloride		Stannous chloride	
Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found
0.1193 g	0.1194 g	0.1127	0.1124
0.2396	0.2394	0.2250	0.2252
0.3588	0.3586	0.3385	0.3383
0.4763	0.4762	0.4513	0.4514

TABLE VI (contd.).

Mercurous chloride.		Pot antim. tartrate.		Arsenious oxide.	
Taken	Found.	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
0.2354 g.	0.2351 g.	0.3240 g.	0.3242 g.	0.0989 g	0.0987 g.
0.4720	0.4718	0.4517	0.4518	0.1979	0.1978
0.7082	0.7081	0.6789	0.6788	0.2866	0.2866
0.9413	0.9412	0.7886	0.7884	0.4598	0.4596

These results show that thalious chloride, stannous chloride, mercurous chloride, potassium antimonyl tartrate and arsenious oxide can be determined quantitatively by the potentiometric method.

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